

Exploring lecturers' experiences in teaching writing skills through online learning

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Abstract

The purpose of this research was to explore the experiences of three lecturers in teaching writing online, the types of online learning platforms used, the techniques employed in teaching writing online, and the challenges faced by the lecturers. This research applied a descriptive qualitative method, and three lecturers participated as respondents in this research. Data were collected through interviews and a checklist questionnaire, and the data were analyzed using content analysis. The results showed that in teaching writing online, the lecturers used some online learning platforms they were familiar with, such as WhatsApp Messenger, Virtual Class, Zoom meeting, and Google Meet. Further, in terms of techniques in teaching writing, it is found that the lecturers use the Picture technique, Reading technique, Teaching organization technique, Controlled writing technique, Mind mapping, and List techniques. It was also found in this research that there were several challenges faced by the lecturers during teaching writing online, including (1) Lecturers faced challenges in controlling students while writing their drafts; (2) Lecturer sometimes face challenges of time management; (3) It takes time to access the online learning platform, and some online platforms require a payment; and lastly, (4) the lecturers have limited access to the internet.

Keywords: *Lecturers' Experiences, Online Learning Platform, Techniques in Teaching Writing*

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Background

Writing is one of the important skills that students have to learn. They can express their ideas, information, thoughts, experiences, and feelings in writing. However, in reality, when expressing their thoughts and feelings in the form of essays or paragraphs, the students still make mistakes.

Writing is a difficult skill to do because students have to generate and organize ideas into good English text. Furthermore, converting ideas into understandable writing is a time-consuming process. Dealing with writing, the students need to pay attention to levels of skills, namely from the low-level skills, such as spelling, punctuation, and word choice, to the high-level skills, such as planning and organizing. Either lecturers or students can easily imagine what will happen to any student dealing with writing if these students have low language proficiency.

Good writing can be seen in completeness, unity, and coherence. Thus, good writing should consider the content, organization, language use or grammar, vocabulary, and mechanics like capitalization, punctuation, spelling, etc. However, it needs a process to achieve a good result. It can be realized by exploring various ways or strategies, or techniques.

Writing activity is carried out in various ways that can represent what approach that is used. In general, the writing process can be categorized into two approaches, namely the product approach and the process approach. Lecturer has the responsibility to make the transferring of their knowledge to the students. Easily in one meeting, the lecturer not only focuses on one of the skills, but the lecturer covers all of the skills in the teaching-learning process. But unfortunately, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the entire teaching and learning process must be done online.

In facilitating the teaching process, lecturers also use several platforms as learning media. Such as WhatsApp, virtual class, Google Meet, and Edmodo. These platforms are expected to be mastered by lecturers because they can facilitate online learning. Teaching techniques also help lecturers create enjoyable activities in the class and make students learn with cheers and enthusiasm. With different types of teaching techniques, both of lecturer and students will enjoy the process of teaching and learning. It is also necessary to have a technique thus students can understand, and the learning objectives conveyed by the lecturer can be conveyed properly. It is not easy to teach online; it takes special skills, good understanding, and professional experience for lecturers to apply online writing techniques. This is the reason for researchers to conduct further research related to the lecturers' experiences in teaching writing online. Thus, the researcher is interested in researching or formulating a research title, such as exploring lecturers' experiences in teaching writing skills through online learning.

Literature Review

Theoretical Foundation of Writing

Brown (1994) in Oktavianingrum (2019) stated that writing is an activity that produces something from the mind that becomes a meaningful text of a sentence. Make good writing by arranging the sequence of sentences. Shortly, writing skills are specific abilities which help writer put their thoughts into words in a meaningful form and mentally interact with the message. Deviani, D. et al (2014) believed that writing is not only a process of linking words into sentence or paragraph, it is a sequence or steps of ideas, organized thoughts and feeling in the form of words and combined into sentence and then into paragraphs in which every sentence is closely related one another.

Moreover, by writing, students are able to deliver their ideas and thoughts in written form. Cheung (2016) said that in teaching writing, we need to explicitly teach the writing processes and the specific strategies to enhance students' writing competence. It is useful for writing teachers to learn the various approaches to teaching writing. However, teachers need to understand that helping students in idea generation and in planning, as well as teaching the rhetorical moves of the particular genres alone, are inadequate in helping students improve their writing.

Writing has a unique position in language teaching since its acquisition involves a practice and knowledge of the other three language skills, such as listening, reading, and speaking. Moreover, it requires mastering other skills, such as metacognitive skills. Learners need to set an objective for their writing, plan it carefully, and think over its layout and logical structure. In the process of writing, they have to use cognitive skills; they have to analyze their sources and then synthesize them in a compact piece of writing. Gaith (2002) in Oktavianingrum (2019) stated that writing is a complex process that allows writers to explore thoughts and ideas on paper. It means that in writing text, the students have to consider many things to build a good writing.

Teaching Writing Online at an EFL Class

Dwahan (2020) stated that online learning faces many challenges, ranging from learners' issues, educators' issues, and content issues. It is a challenge for institutions to engage students and make them participate in the teaching-learning process. It is a challenge for teachers to move from offline mode to online mode, changing their teaching methodologies, and managing their time. It is challenging to develop content that not only covers the curriculum but also engages the students (Kebritchi et al., 2017). The quality of e-learning programs is a real challenge. There is no clear stipulation by the government in their educational policies about e-learning programs. There is a lack of standards for quality, quality control, development of e-resources, and e-content delivery. This problem needs to be tackled immediately so that everyone can enjoy the benefits of quality education via e-learning.

Teaching Writing on an Online Platform

Online learning, as a subset of all distance education, has always been concerned with the provision of access to educational experiences that are, at the least, more flexible in time and in space than campus-based education (Oliver et al., 2009). The most characteristic of online learning is related to flexibility in time and place, students' and instructors' involvement, and different characteristics that online learning shares with distance education. Therefore, online learning might not be ready to serve all disciplines within the same method, and not all online learning environments are similar.

The use of online learning platforms such as WhatsApp Messenger, Google Meet, Zoom meeting, and edmodo has been implemented by some teachers and lecturers as an attempt to integrate technology into the teaching and learning process in the classroom. The online platforms promote both inquiry-based learning and independent learning since the online platforms facilitate interactions between lecturers and students, although they are not in the same room

WhatsApp Messenger

WhatsApp is an internet-based application that is one of the most popular impacts of the development of information technology. According to Larasati, et al (2013), WhatsApp is an

application for instant messaging, and allows us to exchange images, videos, photos, and voice messages, and can be used to share information and discussions. Mutmainnah & Azmina (2020), in their research, said that lecturers can implement five learning activities during writing class in their group. The writing activities are presented below:

- a. The lecturers' first writing activity on the WhatsApp group was to share and explain the writing materials.
- b. After explaining the materials, the lecturer asked the students to engage in a brief discussion about the previously explained materials
- c. After that, the lecturer instructed students on how to construct sentences. The lecturer specified a time limit for composing the sentences.
- d. And then editing sentences. Editing was one of the primary activities in this writing class. Besides composing sentences, students were also expected to edit their sentences to make their sentences more perfect.
- e. Then posting the writing product. Writing is a productive language skill.

Zoom Meeting

In Putra (2020) said that learning activities that can be implemented when using the Zoom application are discussion forums, where students are asked to enter the class via the link and code that has been provided, then start two-way communication materials. Lecturers create a topic that can later be commented on and discussed by students in the online class.

Google Meet

Wahyuni (2021) said that there are several steps to start online learning through Google Meet. First, students are asked to join through the given meeting code. Then the lecturer starts learning with the share screen feature, which is to share material on the screen, then the white board can be used to clarify when the lecturer explains the form of writing, and a chat column that students can use to write down questions or ideas that have not been understood regarding the material presented. Further, the use of Google Meet can also be used for the process of evaluating student attitudes, such as when students convey ideas, thoughts, opinions, or questions related to the material presented by the teacher. Thus, the enthusiasm of students can be seen. Teachers can also easily assess student activity during the online learning process.

Virtual Classes

Virtual classes facilitate interaction between students and learning materials. Likewise, the interaction between students and teachers or lecturers and between fellow students. Students can share information or opinions on various matters relating to lessons and other needs for the self-development of students.

Edmodo

There are three steps in using Edmodo in a writing class. Those steps are preparation, teaching, the learning process, and valuation (Daelani, in Alka and Umamah, 2020).

Techniques in Teaching Writing

Technique is a way that teacher delivers the lesson through classroom activities to reach the learning goal (Brown, 2000:7). Thus, the process of transferring knowledge to the learners in order that learners can know or understand what lecturers have explained.

Techniques in teaching writing focus on what techniques are used by the lecturers and how they apply those techniques in the classroom. The lecturers have to create some steps in order to give instructions that are appropriate for the technique used. There are many kinds of techniques that can be used to teach writing. According to Raimes (1983), there are four techniques used in teaching writing skills, namely:

1. Technique in Using Pictures

In teaching writing teacher can use pictures, drawings, posters, cartoons, or other illustrations. This technique can be used as a teaching aid in the classroom. According to Raimes (1983), using a wordless or picture book, students can create their own narrative. A picture can be media because those can be a valuable resource. The picture provides a shared experience for students in the classroom, a common base that leads to a variety of language activities and also a variety of tasks.

2. Technique in Using Reading

Reading can also be used as a teaching technique in the teaching and learning process. The lecturer can give a stimulus or example by using a reading story, a newspaper, a magazine, or other. According to Raimes (1983), many writing exercises will be assigned based on specific readings; there will be some writing exercises in which the students will be allowed to choose the book or passage that they will read. This should not be difficult to set up a classroom with reading material suitable for this writing unit. Passages for these exercises would most often be chosen by the students themselves.

3. Technique in Controlled Writing

Controlled writing, also known as guided writing, has been a tradition for a long time in English as a second or foreign language classroom. According to Raimes (1983), controlled writing is a useful tool at all levels of composition teaching and not just in the early stages before students get enough fluency to handle free writing. It is still considered an effective tool in helping students put words on paper. Unlike free writing, controlled writing takes place when learners are provided with lots of content and form an outline to complete paragraphs, to manipulate, model to or follow parts to proceed. Also, controlled writing helps in preventing errors that seem to occur from the first language disorder and reinforces the use of a second language pattern.

“In this technique, the trainer will ask some questions to tap the knowledge of the respondents or to obtain their hypotheses or conclusions, and then sort the responses into categories. The guided-teaching method is a nice break from straight lecturing and allows the trainer to learn what participants already know and understand before making instructional points. This method is especially useful when teaching abstract concepts” (Silberman, 2005).

Arumi (2015) said that it belongs to a simple technique because students are still guided by the lecturer with questions. It aims to give students a description of the topic, especially for an

abstract one. It also gives any background knowledge and vocabulary relating to the topic. Then, it is hoped to be able to help students explore the topic in their writing activity.

4. Technique in Teaching Organization

Technique in teaching organization is a technique where the students do a process from general statements to specific ones for the writing (Raimes, 1983). In addition, according to Cali (2003), teaching organization is much more complicated than teaching students the formula for the five-paragraph essay. Although formula writing can help scaffold students' early efforts at writing a particular genre, the scaffolding must eventually be removed to allow students to grow as writers.

a. Outlining

Tazky (2018) in her journal said that an outline is a plan to think and organize some ideas that will be arranged into a good writing before writing a paper or essay, or a form plan to think and organize some ideas that will be arranged into a good writing. Students will be able to learn more about the subject being covered if they use an outline. Furthermore, the outline structure includes the subject and particular information regarding the topic to be presented.

b. Analyzing

An analysis is a thorough examination of a subject. It entails conducting research and breaking down the results into smaller pieces. This technique is used to analyze the details of students' writing; it presents their specific argument about a topic and backs it up with evidence.

However, there are also some techniques in teaching writing by Silberman (2005):

1. Index-Card Match Technique

Silberman (2005) stated that to create an index-card matching activity, the trainer writes each tool on a card and the definition on a separate card. The cards are combined and shuffled. Each participant receives a card (either a term or a definition) and then finds its match. Arumi (2015) also believed that it would help students actively participate in the writing process. It will also help the class atmosphere be cheerful and pleasant, and sometimes a bit noisy.

2. Team-Quiz Technique

Silberman (2005) said that this technique is an enjoyable and non-threatening way to increase the participants' accountability for what they are learning from a lecture or presentation. Arumi (2015) also stated that the quiz-team technique is a technique for writing activity by giving quizzes or questions to the students working in groups.

It can be concluded that teaching techniques are ways or efforts made by teachers or lecturers in the implementation of the learning process. In implementing the learning process, lecturers need to understand various techniques well.

Research Method

This research used a qualitative descriptive method. Qualitative method is a process of scientific research that is intended to understand human problems in a social context by creating a

comprehensive and complex picture, reporting detailed views of sources of information, and carried out in the natural setting (Creswell 2009). Content analysis is a scientific technique for interpreting text or content. Krippendorff (2004) defines content analysis as a research technique to infer the meaning of a text through reliable procedures, which can be replicated or applied in different contexts (replicable) and are legitimate. This research was conducted at one of the Universities in East Indonesia. Three Lecturers participated in this study. They have been teaching writing courses at the University level for more than 5 years offline. There were two data collection techniques were used: questionnaire and interview. There were closed-ended questionnaire consisted of 20 closed-ended items related to the participants' experience. The interviews were used to gain in-depth explanations and descriptions of the lecturers' experiences in teaching writing online. Data analysis is the process of simplifying data into a form that is easier to understand, and the process of teaching and learning. Content analysis was used. There were six steps of analyzing data proposed by Creswell (2009):

The first step is to organize and prepare the data for analysis. This involves transcribing interviews. Optically scanning material. Typing up field notes, or sorting and arranging the data into different types depending on the sources of information. *The second, read through all the data.* This step deals with obtaining a general sense of the information and reflecting on its overall meaning. *The third step is the coding process.* Coding is the process of organizing the material into chunks or segments of text before bringing meaning to information (Creswell, 2009). It involves taking text data or pictures gathered during data collection, segmenting sentences (or paragraphs) or images into categories, and labeling those categories with a term, often a term based on the actual language of the participant (called an in vivo term). The four steps are using the coding process to generate a description of the setting or people, as well as categories or themes for analysis. *Description* involves a detailed rendering of information about people, places, or events in a setting. Researchers can generate codes for this description. The fifth step is how the description and themes will be represented in the qualitative narrative. The most popular approach is to use a narrative passage to convey the findings of the analysis. This might be a discussion that mentions a chronology of events, the detailed discussion of several themes (complete with subthemes, specific illustrations, multiple perspectives from individuals, and quotations), or a discussion with interconnecting themes, and a final step in data analysis involves making an *interpretation* or meaning of the data.

Findings and Discussion

The result of data analysis was divided into Teaching Writing Experience in Teaching Online, Teaching Materials, Online Learning Platform, and Various Techniques in Teaching Writing.

Teaching Writing Experience

This research found that three lecturers who participated in this research have different qualifications in the period of teaching.

Table 1. Teaching Writing Experience

Theme	Description	
Categorization	Code	Subcode
Lecturer qualification	L1	More than 5 years
	L2	14 years
	L3	17 years

The data analysis shows that each respondent has different qualifications. First lecturer (L1) said that *“I have been teaching writing for more than five years”*. Different from L1, the second lecturer (L2) claimed that he has been teaching writing for almost 14 years. *“I have been teaching writing since 2007, odd semester”*. Furthermore, the third lecturer (L3) stated that she has been teaching writing at Khairun University for about 17 years. *“I have been teaching writing started from 2003 until now”*.

Experiences in Teaching Online

Teaching writing requires knowledge of the general writing process, such as understanding different approaches to prewriting, and that revision means more than just editing. Teaching writing, lecturers draw on knowledge of varied processes aligned with producing particular written genres.

Table 2. Experience in Teaching Online

Theme	Description
Categorization	Code
Experience in teaching online	- Easy to share materials.
	- Utilizing existing technology media.
	- Spend more time because we can not meet the students.
	- Very limited time when using the online learning platform.

Interview data show that the lecturers proposed that teaching online has advantages and disadvantages. Table 2 shows that both L1 and L3 viewed advantages in teaching online are that easy to share material and utilize existing technology media. L1 stated that *“my experience in teaching online, it is easy when we share the materials”*. On the other hand, L3 also claimed that

“in online teaching, we use virtual class to be absent and upload material, then we meet via Zoom”.

Furthermore, it can also be seen in Table 2 that the disadvantage of teaching writing online is time management. L1 mentioned that *“it is difficult when we apply the exercises online. We also need many time to reach out to all students”*. As well as the L1 perspective of disadvantages of teaching online experiences, L2 pointed out that *“teaching online is difficult. We have to spend more time because we cannot meet students directly”*. There are other experiences proposed by the lecturers in teaching writing online based on the results of the interview data.

Teaching Materials

Learning is a process of students’ interaction with lecturers and learning resources in a learning environment. Learning can be said as a process of helping students gain knowledge, skills, and define their attitude. These all deal with how the materials are prepared and delivered.

Table 3: Teaching Materials

Theme	Description
Categorization	Code
Teaching materials	Preparing RPS and learning media.

Interview data showed that respondents sent the materials in the form of PowerPoint and images. The respondent also provided lesson plans as materials for guidance on teaching in several meetings. L1 stated that *“I prepare RPS or lesson plan before starting teaching”*. L2 claimed that he prepared RPS and materials in the form of a PowerPoint before teaching writing. *“RPS and materials are definitely prepared”*. In the same way, L3 also argued that in the process of teaching materials, she sent the material first to the students. She commented: *“I prepare RPS and some materials. Usually, it is shared at the beginning of the meeting. The RPS covers meeting 1-16”*.

Online Learning Platform

Online learning platforms can be used as learning media. These online platforms have also been widely used as learning alternatives in many situations. One of them is in the education sector.

Table 4: Online Learning Platform

Theme	Description
Categorization	Code
Online Learning Platform	- Whatsapp messenger - Virtual class - Zoom meeting - Google meet. - Edmodo

The data analysis in Table 4 above, the online learning platform can be divided into: (1) most platforms used, (2) rarely used, and (3) not used. In most platforms used, L1 and L3 have the same thing in using online learning platforms; they used Virtual class (VC), WhatsApp messenger (WM), and Zoom meeting (ZM). L1 stated that “*in online learning, the most platforms that I used are Virtual class (VC), WhatsApp messenger (WM), and Zoom meeting (ZM)*”. L3 also argued that “*I used Virtual class (VC), WhatsApp messenger (WM), and Zoom meeting (ZM) in online learning*”. Meanwhile, L2 said the most platforms that he used are: Virtual class (VC) and Zoom meeting (ZM). L2 stated that “*I often use (VC) and (ZM)*”.

Furthermore, the rarely used platform by respondents is Google Meet (GM). L1 said that “*I used Google Meet (GM) once at the beginning of online learning*”. The last is an online platform that was not used by respondents, Edmodo (E).

WhatsApp Messenger

WhatsApp is an internet-based platform that is one of the most popular impacts of the development of information technology. This internet-based platform has the potential to be used as a communication medium because it makes it easier for users to communicate with each other

Table 5: WhatsApp Messenger

Theme	Description
Categorization	Code
Whatsapp messenger	WhatsApp is used to send materials.

As shown in Table 5, three respondents used WhatsApp Messenger only in sending material and information in groups that had been created previously. L1 and L3 said that they used WM for sending materials, the same as Virtual Class.

Virtual Class

Virtual classes facilitate interaction between students and learning materials. Likewise, the interaction between students and teachers or lecturers and fellow students. Students can share information or opinions on various matters relating to lessons and other needs for the self-development of students. Teachers or lecturers can place teaching materials online that can be downloaded by students, assign assignments to students, and collect them through virtual classes that have been provided.

Table 6 Virtual Class

Theme	Description
Categorization	Subcode
Virtual class	A virtual class is used to send materials and then give feedback to students.

It cannot directly
comment on students'
work.

As Table 6 shows, there are advantages and disadvantages of using Virtual Class (VC). Respondents agree that VC is a good platform for sending materials and giving feedback to students. Same as WhatsApp (WM). The disadvantage of this platform is, it can not directly comment on students' work. L2 stated that *“the problem of VC is that we cannot comment directly on students' writing and just give feedback, even though only via WhatsApp and students' personal e-mail”*.

Zoom Meeting (ZM)

Zoom cloud meeting is an alternative platform for virtual meetings to facilitate communication between lecturers and students without making direct contact, and be able to support learning needs in today's digital era.

Table 7 Zoom Meeting

Theme	Description
Categorization	Code
Zoom meeting	Zoom is good because it can be face-to-face.
	Have limited time and an unsupported connection quality.

The result showed that there are advantages and disadvantages in using Zoom meetings (ZM). It can be seen in Table 7. L3 said that ZM has an advantage in teaching online. *“We can directly monitor students even though in virtual”*. L2 also commented that he enjoyed using the ZM platform, but a bad connection is the problem. It made the teaching online process not optimal. L1 said that *“the disadvantage of this platform is that: has limited time in teaching online, except for those who pay monthly”*.

Google Meet (GM)

Similar to ZM, the GM platform also provides an online distance learning experience. GM can be accessed using the web, Android, and iOS systems. The GM can also accommodate more than 100 participants. But unfortunately, from the data of the interviews, only one out of three respondents used this platform.

Table 8 Google Meet

Theme	Description
Categorization	Code
Google meet	Rarely use Google Meet. It's just the beginning of online learning.

The results showed that two of three respondents did not use Google Meet as an online learning platform (GM). Meanwhile, one respondent used GM only at the beginning of the implementation of online learning. L1 stated that “*I used GM once at the beginning of online learning*”.

Edmodo (E)

Edmodo is a social media concept of virtual education that helps lecturers and students in a form of a new style of learning. Current developments have led to a change in the way students learning with technological developments.

Table 9 Edmodo

Theme	Description
Categorization	Code
Edmodo	Do not use this platform.

The data analysis in Table 9 showed that three respondents did not use Edmodo (E) as an online platform. L1 and L3 have the same arguments that they did not use Edmodo (E) in teaching online. L2 stated that “*I did not use Edmodo (E), but I heard that Edmodo (E) is a good platform*”.

Various Techniques in Teaching Writing (VTW)

Technique is a way that a teacher delivers the lesson through classroom activities in order to reach the learning goal. Techniques in teaching writing focus on what techniques are used by the lecturers and how they apply those techniques in the classroom. The lecturers have to create some steps in order to give instructions that are appropriate for the technique used.

Table 10: Various Techniques in Teaching Writing

Theme	Description
Categorization	Code
Various techniques in	- Technique in using pictures - Technique in teaching organization - Technique in using reading

teaching writing	- Technique in controlled writing - Index match card technique - Quiz team technique - Mind mapping - List group label
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The data analysis in Table 10 above, techniques in teaching writing (VTW) can be divided into: (1) most techniques implemented and not implemented in teaching online. Most techniques implemented, L1 stated that he implemented the reading technique (TR) and controlled writing technique (TCW). Furthermore, L2 and L3 mentioned that they were implementing the picture technique (TP), reading technique (TR), controlled writing technique (TCW), and teaching organization technique (TO). (*ZM in online learning*). Meanwhile, observe from interview data, found out that L2 also implemented two other techniques in teaching online, out of material in Chapter two. “*beside techniques that I mentioned, I also implemented mind mapping (MM) and list group label (LGL) as teaching techniques*”.

Techniques that were not implemented by respondents are: Index match card technique and Quiz team technique. L3 said that “*quiz team technique was not implemented due to pandemic conditions, which required students to study from home, and there were no study groups*”.

Technique in Using Pictures

In teaching writing, lecturers can use pictures, drawings, posters, cartoons, or other illustrations. This technique can be used as a teaching aid and used in the classroom.

Table 11: Technique in Using Pictures

Theme	Description
Categorization	Code
Techniques in using pictures	Using picture technique is used to teach descriptive writing.

The data analysis in Table 11, the picture technique is used to describe an image, place, and other things to simulate students’ attention. L3 said that TP is usually used in teaching descriptive writing.

Techniques in Using Reading

Reading can also be used as a teaching technique in the teaching and learning process. The lecturer can give a stimulus or example by using a reading story, a newspaper, a magazine or etc.

Table 12: Technique in Using Reading

Theme	Description
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Categorization	Code
Techniques in using reading	Students read articles found on the internet and then make it an experience in writing new texts.

The data analysis in Table 12, three respondents used the Technique in using Reading (TR). L2 said “*in reading technique, students need to read articles from internet to make they understand what they were reading, more critically and having experience in writing new texts*”. L3 also said that “*reading technique is implemented because every materials that we shared, it needs to read firs then you can understand the instruction*”.

Technique in Controlled Writing

Controlled writing, also known as guided writing, has been a tradition for a long time in English as a second or foreign language classroom.

Table 13 Technique in Controlled Writing

Theme	Description
Categorization	Code
Technique in controlled writing	Controlled writing helps in preventing errors that seem to occur from the first language disorder and reinforces the use of a second language pattern.

The data analysis in Table 13, the technique in controlled writing (TCW) is used to control students' writing organization. L1 said that lecturers give topics to students and then control students' writing organization. Directing students in each writing section. L1 and L3 mentioned that an example of control writing is writing a proposal background. Students are asked to write within the allotted time, and after that, they are given feedback.

Techniques in Teaching Organization

Teaching an organization is much more complicated than teaching students the formula for the five-paragraph essay. Although formula writing can help scaffold students' early efforts at writing a particular genre, the scaffolding must eventually be removed to allow students to grow as writers.

Table 14: Technique in Teaching Organization

Theme	Description
Categorization	Code
Techniques in teaching organization	Explain writing organizations in detail to students.

The data analysis shows that two of three respondents use this technique in teaching online. Organization technique is a technique where the students do a process from general statements to specific ones for writing. **L2** said that “*teaching organization technique is explaining writing organization in detail to students*”. In addition, according to **L3**, “*TO is used to ask students to reorganize the writings or articles they have read*”.

Mind Mapping (MM)

Mind mapping is a graphical way to represent ideas and concepts. It is a visual thinking tool that helps structure information, helping to analyze, comprehend, synthesize, recall, and generate new ideas.

Table 15 Mind Mapping

Theme	Description
Categorization	Code
Mind mapping	Mind mapping is used to increase students' learning motivation and skills.

As Table 15 shows, two of three respondents did not use this technique. While one other respondent often used. **L2** said that “*mind mapping (MM) is a technique that is used to increase students' learning motivation and skills because it makes it easier for them to be creative in expressing their thoughts and compiling/organizing ideas in written form*”. This technique is not included in Chapter Two; this technique was obtained when interviewing **L2** in the field. Used as one of teaching writing techniques.

List-Group Label (LGL)

List group label is a strategy that makes students create their own words; they look for words from the dictionary related to the topic.

Table 16 List-Group Label

Theme	Description
Categorization	Code
List-group label	Help students to organize and remember new words in writing sentences.

As Table 16 shows, two of three respondents did not use this technique. Meanwhile, one respondent often used in teaching writing. **L2** said that this technique is used to help students organize and remember new words in writing sentences; this technique was obtained when interviewing **L2** in the field.

Challenges in Teaching Writing Online (CTO)

This research found that three lecturers, who participated in this research, face some challenges in teaching writing online.

Table 17: Challenges in Teaching Writing Online

Theme	Description
Categorization	Code
Challenges in teaching writing online	- Can not see the students' draft directly. - Limited time in teaching through an online learning platform. - Bad connection.

As Table 17 shows, there are several challenges (**CTO**) found in online learning. **L1** stated that when teaching online, sometimes he faced a bad internet connection. **L2** commented that when he teaches online, sometimes he does not know the text that students collect, written by themselves or copied and pasted, because he cannot control it directly. **L3** said that in using the online platform, there is a limited time for those who do not pay monthly.

Conclusion

The researcher concluded that in teaching writing experience, lecturers are familiar with implementing online learning. Further, it is easy to share material through online platforms. Online platforms utilized in this research were: WhatsApp Messenger, Virtual class, Zoom meeting, and

Google Meet. Mostly techniques that have been used by lecturers in teaching writing online were: Picture technique, Reading technique, teaching organization technique, controlled writing technique, Mind mapping, and List group. Challenges faced by the lecturers during teaching writing online were: (1) lecturers cannot see the students' draft directly. (2) Have limited time in using online media except for those who pay monthly. (3) Unsupported internet quality. Some suggestions related to the problems are: (1) students need to increase their writing practice because it is important. (2) Make a habit of studying independently from home. Motivated them to start learning.

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